

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

ON GENERALIZATION OF THE EIGENVALUE PROBLEM IN QUANTUM MEASUREMENT: A MEASUREMENT THAT WOULD BE BETTER NOT TO EXIST

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Abstract

In his work "Against 'measurement'" [Physics World, August, 33-40 (1990)], J. Bell mentioned Dirac as the most distinguished of 'why bother?'ers since P. Dirac in his paper 'The Evolution of the Physicist's Picture of Nature' [Sci. Amer. **208**(5), 45-53 (1963)] considered the difficulties (or 'misunderstandings', according to N. Bohr) of quantum mechanics and divided them into two classes. Into the first class he particularly referred the problems of 'observer' and 'measurement'. Dirac suggested that these problems should be left for later.

This work is an attempt to review the above problems, both based on our own point of view and on the analysis of the works of our predecessors (mainly in footnotes to avoid casting a shadow on the former). This attempt results in a new analytical model of the measuring experiment, the conclusions of which are also discussed.

Keywords: Measurement, Observation, Observable, von Neumann Measurement Postulate, Interaction Energy Operator.

A brief analysis of the processes of measurement common to any science reveal paradox. This paradox is encountered when one tries to make clear formal statements are related to experience in such a way that factual statements, such as statements about measurements, result. I believe that this paradox bears an analogy to the "fallacy of the third man" which disturbed Plato.

E.G. Ballard [1]

1. Preamble

With its reticence, its understatement and under-visibility (or under-observability, if the readers like) that quantum mechanics challenges for more than a hundred years [2,3]⁷, it reminds me the well-known Zen Ryoanji Temple Garden in Kyoto which is a small rectangular area, 30 m long from east to west, and 10 m from south to north, covered with white gravel, and composed of 15 black unprocessed stones gathered in five groups. Let us name it as the *Garden reality*.

2. Portrait of Observer: Observable⁸

⁷ I presume that the period between 1900, when Planck put forward the hypothesis of quanta (his son Erwin Planck recalls that once, walking in Grunewald near Berlin with his father, the latter said: "Today I have made a discovery as important as that of Newton" ([4, 5]), and 1925-26, the birth of the aforementioned works, was determined by the impossibility of proposing a quantum theory that would be free from the concepts of classical mechanics. Despite the significant success of Bohr's theory in understanding the physical and chemical properties of atoms and molecules, it and the resulted Copenhagen interpretation were not logically closed: it contradictorily combined the laws of classical mechanics and quantum postulates.

⁸ G. Jaeger ([6], p. 62) notes: "Bell (see [7], p. 170) argued that the use of the term observable can be misleading, much as Bethe argued that the term uncertainty can be: "There is

The problem of a measurement on the object is thereby transformed into the problem of an observation on the apparatus.

E.P. Wigner (p.9, [24])

No matter from which point the garden visitor, - define him the Observer - views, observes or watches this reality, the fifteenth stone is always out of sight, obscured by other stones. Sometimes, however, it seems as if 15 stones are visible, since individual stones, due to their irregular shape, are perceived as two. It is only possible to fully observe all the stones by floating in the air above that *Garden reality* and looking down on it from above. I suggest that the observer does only observe of what lies before his eyes, without thereby violating the properties, structure of the observed object or objects. On one hand, it is type of the "detached observer"⁹. On the other, it excludes a so-called effect of observer. Let explain the latter.

Everything around us is an object (a thing, a phenomenon). They compose the nature ("*physis*", "*φύσις*", in the ancient Greek¹⁰), the *reality* that is studied by *physics* as the science of 'physis', the nature of

indeed much talk of 'observables' in quantum theory books. And from some popular presentations the general public could get the impression that the very existence of the cosmos depends on our being here to observe the observables. I do not know that this is wrong. I am inclined to hope that we are indeed that important.

But I see no evidence that this is so in the success of contemporary quantum theory."

⁹ This term was used by A. Einstein in his dialogue with N. Bohr at the Fifth Solvay Congress in 1927 on the principles of the Copenhagen interpretation of quantum mechanics, which, however, did not yet have such a name, introduced only in the 1950s [8-12].

¹⁰ Note the consonance of the words 'physis' and 'physics'. Let us remember the following words of Aristotle from his "Metaphysics" ([13], Book I (A); first sentence): " ALL men

things or phenomena. This study of reality on a so called scientific method, i.e. the empirical method for acquiring a knowledge that is based on the postulate (or assumption) that reality exists independently of observer as an objective reality (tautology, in some sense). The observation is the basis of describing this objective reality that manifests itself in physical phenomena. Let us remember this statement.

Under the action of observation, an observer observes the thing(s) around him by means of his senses and/or (macroscopic) instrument(s) (or apparatus). The effect of observer assumes that these senses can influence thing(s) so significantly that they can change them – actually this is a disturbance of an observed system by the act of observation: often it is the result of the instrument(s) that an observer utilizes by necessity and less often by his senses. Although, it is worth remembering that these senses themselves may have a limited use.

The act of observation is always related with the observer's memory, or the capacity of brain: with necessity he memorizes the observed thing(s) as a result of observation. The capabilities of human's memory (of brain) are not unlimited [19], and therefore a given observer can remember (photograph) only a certain segment in the act of observation. Definitely, this segment is not a whole picture of the nature or reality. To form a complete picture of reality from these pieces, segments, a given observer should communicate with another observer, and the latter with the other, and so on. This requires a next step in the procedure of observation. Note that these are applicable in a macroscopic world.

A microscopic, sub-atomic, or quantum world is essentially different¹¹. As Feynman noted: "If I say they [the electrons and light – E.S.K.] behave like particles I give the wrong impression; also if I say they behave like waves. They behave on their own inimitable way, which technically could be called a quantum mechanical way. They behave in a way that is like nothing that you have ever seen before, Your experience with things that you have seen before is incomplete. The behaviour of things on a very tiny scale is simply different. An atom does not behave like a weight hanging on a spring

and oscillating. Nor does it behave like a miniature representation of the solar system with little planets going around in orbits. Nor does it appear to be somewhat like a cloud or fog of some sort surrounding the nucleus. It behaves like nothing you have ever seen before." ([20], p.128).

And this is true: it is impossible to look at, touch, poke a typical quantum object, since the spectrum of visible radiation, lying in the range from 380 to 720 nanometers, is approximately 2000 times larger than the size (diameter) of an atom, which is 10-8 cm (and the nucleus is about 10-13 cm) ([20], p. 2-4, 2-2. Physics before 1920)¹².

The act of observation turns into the act of being observable. It turns out that the quantum, subatomic world, which is supposedly described by quantum mechanics, itself needs observers (and, looking ahead, measuring equipment (see [21] for references). Let now introduce the term 'observable' as the observer who has an ability to observe, or as the observer who equipped by the method of observation, the scientific method, that determine the properties of what is observed¹³. Kant defines this transition from observation to observable as follows: "There is no doubt whatever that all our cognition begins with experience, for how else should the cognitive faculty be awakened into exercise if not through objects that stimulate our senses and in part themselves produce representations, in part bring the activity of our understanding into motion to compare these, to connect or separate them, and thus in work up the raw material of sensible impressions into a cognition of objects that is called experience? As far as time is concerned, then, no cognition in us precedes experience, and with experience every cognition begins." ([23], p.136¹⁴), whereas Feynman introduces the intermediate phase: "Observation, reason, and experi-

by nature desire to know" (compare with Descartes in his "Meditation 2": "cogito ergo sum"). The definition "to know", according to Merriam-Webster (since 1828), is "1. to perceive directly: have direct *cognition* of; 2. to have *understanding* of; 3. to recognize as *being* the same as something previously known". So, for example, the word "science" (scientia) means in Latin "knowledge" (see in English "knowledge": recall the above definition of fundamental science). This desire, applied to physis, prompted Aristotle to introduce a discipline whose purpose is to gain knowledge about physis as "physics" (in Greek: Φυσική ἀκρόασις *Phusike akroasis*; in ancient Greek: τὰ φυσικά, that means "the [writings] on nature" or "*natural philosophy*". In Latin: *Physica*, or *Naturales Auscultationes*, possibly meaning "*lectures on nature*"). (Part 2, Book II [14]; see also [15]) (see ([16], p.85 и Part 2, Book II [14]). It is perhaps also worth mentioning here the recent discussion on "What is Physics" on the pages of Physics Today [17,18].

¹¹ It seems that the etymology of some of these words is rather similar: 'atom' from the ancient Greek *ἄτομος* meaning 'indivisible', 'incut'; 'quantum' from the Latin *quantus* meaning

'how much', that is 'elementary discrete indivisible fraction'. Generally speaking, these two words stress the idea of a discreteness in nature.

¹² For this reason, I think the legend of Democritus (460 B.C. ~370 B.C.) supposedly sitting on a rock by the sea and cutting an apple into an indivisible particle of apple matter (atom) is definitely a myth. A myth is defined as a statement that is accepted without proper grounds and does not, in principle, admit of experimental demonstration. On the contrary, the atomic fission was discovered by O.Hahn, F. Strassmann and L. Meitner, and O.R. Frisch in 1938-39.

¹³ Dirac echoes (p. 34, [22]): "When we make an observation we measure some dynamical variable."

¹⁴ On p.716 [23], Kant defines experience as "perception with rules". Later, he defines experience as "the agreement of perceptions (of empirical representations) to the cognition of an object".

ment”¹⁵ ([24], p. 2-2)¹⁶ (the second phase refers to what Wiener on p. 307 [29] noted as ‘psychology’¹⁷).

3. Measurement

... Any theory that has certain properties has a measurement problem.

N. Ormrod, V. Vilasini, and J. Barrett [30]

3.1. Introduction

This is how we approach the key topic of this work – the measurement [1,31,32]. The paradigm of measurement is inherent to the whole building of physics. permeates the entire essence of quantum mechanics [23-59], and links it to classical mechanics since, generally speaking, the concept of observer does not only include human sense organs rather devices or measuring apparatuses¹⁸. Fock [61] (see also [62]) notes that “there is no fundamental difference between the two. For example, glasses correct defects of the eye lens, microscopes and telescopes greatly expand the possibilities of observation.” However, the applications of apparatus are based on certain abstractions: One is the absolutization of physical processes: that is, the assumption that they occur “by themselves” and are not disturbed by the act of observation, and therefore do not require further instructions on the methods of observation. As quantum mechanics proves, this assumption is fulfilled only approximately.

So, the measuring apparatuses expand the known limited capabilities of human sense organs. It is assumed that they consist of a large number of particles composing some classical ensembles which are described by coherent quantum superpositions of sufficiently many and macroscopically distinct states [45,46,63]. All this results in the following [32]:

Quantum Measurement Problem: *Given a specific basis (or context), quantum mechanics describes mathematically a quantum state in terms of a superposition of, in general, multiple states. Since the evolution described by quantum mechanics allows us to predict*

that the quantum system will get entangled with the apparatus and thus its pointer positions will also become a superposition, the question is why do we observe a single outcome instead of a superposition of them?

It is absolutely clear that the quantum measurement problem disappears if the measuring apparatus is microscopic. There are several examples [57] of this.

3.2. Measuring Experiment¹⁹

Under a measuring experiment which Fock [64] claims as a phenomenon (an experience), the above (in Section 2.) order of cognition is simply reversed: performing a measurement, an observer observes its outcome(s) or property(ies). As part of the controversy with Bohr over his article [65] in *Dialectica*²⁰, Fock [66] defined three stages of a measuring experiment in quantum mechanics in which the actual measurement constitutes only its last stage. It is preceded by the following two stages: **i.** The stage of preparation of the observed (unperturbed) phenomenon itself²¹ and **ii.** The stage of the behavior of an object under fixed external conditions, which alone is the subject of description by quantum mechanics.

Therefore, considering a measurement as a phenomenon, the former is described quantum mechanically. Speaking generally, say within the Copenhagen interpretation, a quantum system is characterized by a state vector. The latter – according to Wigner [34], ‘this is an almost verbatim quotation of von Neumann’ [67] – changes in two ways. One is with time, obeys Schrodinger time-dependent equation of motion of quantum mechanics and change occurs continuously. The other one is a discontinuous and is often called the ‘reduction’ or ‘collapse’ of a state vector [67,68]²².

Let us end this Subsection with the concept of “contextuality” [69]. We have already met the word “context” in formulation of the **Quantum Measurement Problem**. By definition, *context* is a complex of conditions under which the measurement is performed

¹⁵ Within quantum mechanics, this refers to a measuring experiment.

¹⁶ The difference between the observer and the observable is demonstrated, as I believe, in the famous story about Einstein and the moon told by Pais [25] (also [26-28]): “It must have been around 1950. I was accompanying Einstein on a walk from The Institute for Advanced Study to his home, when he suddenly stopped, turned to me, and asked me if I really believed that the moon exists only if I look at it.” Rigorously, there are actually two acts: Act 1 – the observer’s observation of the moon; Act 2 – If I do not look at the object, is it the moon? To answer this question, it is necessary to know the properties of the moon that fully identify it. This is achieved by experience, an experiment that determines, or “measures” its properties (identifications). With the readers’ permission, I equate the words ‘experiment’ and ‘measurement’.

¹⁷ “The distinction between psychology, logic, and epistemology is a commonplace. The first treats of experience as an act, experience in its relation to the individual observer. The second concerns itself with the internal marks by which truth may be distinguished from error, and in so far as it deals with experience, has to do with some sort of validity of the experience as evidence of a truth. The third discusses in a general way all the elements—observer, object, immediate presentation—which enter into the experience.”

¹⁸ Interestingly, the authors of the famous EPR paper [60] restricted to human experience only: “The correctness of the theory is judged by the degree of agreement between the conclusions of the theory and human experience” (p. 777).

¹⁹ I choose some consensus on Bell’s point of view (p.34 [44], see also [6]): “Even in a low-brow practical account, I think it would be good to replace the word ‘measurement’, in the formulation, by the word ‘experiment’.”

²⁰ The history of this article is as follows. In 1948, on the pages of this journal, then published in Switzerland, a discussion took place on the fundamental problems of quantum mechanics, in which N. Bohr, W. Pauli, A. Einstein, W. Heisenberg, L. de Broglie, H. Reichenbach and others took part.

²¹ Here Fock argues with Bohr’s assertion [66]: “As a more appropriate way of expression, one may strongly advocate limitation of the use of the word *phenomenon* to refer exclusively to observations obtained under specified circumstances, including an account of the whole experiment.” (Compare with Kant’s [23] thesis on the existence of *phenomenon* and *nomenon*). Fock [69] also notes that “Bohr repeatedly emphasized that measurement is associated with “uncontrolled interaction” between the object and the device.

²² The attempts to obtain the second kind of the state-vector change from the first one by v. Neumann [67] and Wigner [34] were failed (see also p. 110 of [68]).

(p. ix, [69])²³. It is clear that this notion is related to the stage **i** of preparation of quantum measuring experiment.

3.3. Modeling of Measuring Experiment

Quantum Phenomena do not occur in a Hilbert space.

They occur in a laboratory. –

Asher Peres [77]

All I'm concerned with is that the theory should predict

the results of measurements.

Stephen Hawking (1994)²⁴

The starting point in a model scenario of a measuring experiment is to partition the complete experimental system **S** into a quantum subsystem **Q**, which is undertaken for performing an experiment by an observable **O**, and a measuring apparatus (instrumental subsystem naturally equipped with a pointer) **A**: $\mathbf{S} = \mathbf{Q} \cup \mathbf{A}$. It is traditionally asserted the macroscopic nature of the latter²⁵. Next, we prepare the state Ψ_i of **Q** for measuring is conducted by the apparatus **A** that *interacts with Q via* the interaction potential \hat{O} .

In order to logically proceed, we present the following statements:

Postulate 1 ([68], p. 6; see also [66] and §§ 10,77 of [22]): A physical observable **A** is represented by a self-adjoint operator \hat{A} in complex Hilbert space **H**.

Postulate 2 ([68], p. 6): Any self-adjoint operator \hat{a} represents a physical observable **a**.

In the other words, the terms ‘measurement’ and ‘mutual interaction’ are equivalent, in some sense. The outcome of a given measuring experiment, described by \hat{O} , on the initial state Ψ_i is the product state Ψ_f , i.e., explicitly,

$$\hat{O} \Psi_i = \Psi_f. \quad (1)$$

This is the general scheme of considering (or interpreting) any measuring experiment. In mathematical terms, Eq.(1) is, in some sense, a generalized eigenvalue problem. At this point the logical model of the measuring experiment ends and is usually formulated

in terms of a series of statements, considered by some as theorems [39] (see also p.39 of [44] and [59]), by others as axioms [35], and by others as postulates [68]. To the last refers the well-known von Neumann measurement postulate [66,68] and [47] which is formulated as follows (according to [68], Projection Postulate): “

Postulate 3: “Let **a** be a physical observable represented by a self-adjoint operator \hat{a} having a purely discrete non-degenerate spectrum. Any measurement of **a** on the quantum state wave function $\Psi(\tau)$ at the time $t = \tau$ induces transition from this state Ψ into one of the eigenfunctions χ_k^a of the operator \hat{a} : $\hat{a}\chi_k^a = \lambda_k\chi_k^a$. The probability for finding λ_k in this transition is equal to (Eq. (1). [39]):

$$P = |\langle \chi_k^a | \Psi(\tau) \rangle|^2. \quad (2)$$

If a given measurement’s outcome is λ_k , this implies that the wave function abruptly changes from $\Psi(\tau)$ into χ_k^a .

The Projection Postulate, often referred to the “reduction” or “collapse” one, corresponds to such time-evolution process that differs from the one, typical in quantum mechanics which is described by the time-dependent Schrödinger equation. As van Kampen [39] emphasizes, all this adds ‘a new postulate to the Schrödinger quantum mechanics’ and ‘the collapse can be used to prepare a system in a certain state χ_k^a ’. This Postulate is limited by that a self-adjoint operator \hat{a} which represents a physical observable **a** has a non-degenerate spectrum. This constraint is overcome by Lüders Projection Postulate which Lüders proposed in 1951 (see also p.14 of [68]).

Let us make a pause to rethink these Postulates. The Projective one interprets a measurement of a physical observable **a** on a given quantum system as that projects the latter into one of the eigenstates of the measuring operator \hat{a} . This is a so called projective measurement whose concept is actually a central paradigm of physics [38]. I suggest that the concept of measurement in quantum mechanics should necessarily include the following immutable truths:

* The observation and measurement of a quantum system perturbs its state.²⁶

²³ In classical physical theories, measuring experiments that are performed simultaneously to a given one are called the latter’s context [70]. In the other words, the context of a given measuring experiment is independent on the other, simultaneously measured experiments. Due to Kochen-Specker theorem, precisely, Bell-Kochen-Specker theorem [71,72] (see also [73]) stating that there exists a contradiction between two basic assumptions of the hidden variable theories which are intended to reproduce the results of quantum mechanics: that all hidden variables corresponding to quantum-mechanical observables have definite values at any given time, and that the values of those variables are intrinsic and independent of the device used to measure them.” (see also wiki), this independence is no longer valid in quantum theory. This is called quantum contextuality [74]. Interestingly, the experiment recently described in [75] does not allow to make conclusions

about contextuality that is concluded from that the measurement of the observables as well as the preparation of the state manifestly depend on the chosen context [76].

²⁴ During a debate with Roger Penrose in 1994 at the Isaac Newton Institute for Mathematical Sciences at the University of Cambridge, transcribed in *The Nature of Space and Time* (1996) by Stephen Hawking and Roger Penrose, p. 121: https://en.wikiquote.org/wiki/Stephen_Hawking . .

²⁵ [90], p. 2; [44], p. 40. The construction of the entire system that can be viewed as a tensor product ‘quantum system’ \otimes ‘measuring instrument’ is discussed in [79].

²⁶ It is difficult to say who first made this statement. Though, for the first time, I read it in Fock [61], von Neumann [66], and de Broglie [80].

* “In quantum theory, every measurement entails a choice. If we choose to measure one observable (physical variable), we choose *not* to measure some other observable” (p.25, [51]).

* Partial measurement, where full wave function collapse is not the only outcome, provides a detailed test of the measurement process. As demonstrated in experiments on superconducting phase qubits, the effect of such measurements can be *undone* and the initial state can be recovered. [52,53]. In the other words, the projective measurement is an irreversible process.

* The measurement and its effect enter the theory as a fundamental notion through one of its axioms [54]. Measurement can be modelled as a physical *interaction* between two systems, “*object*” and “*apparatus*” (see also [35]). Thus, we have measurement-as-axiom and measurement-as-interaction. Quantum mechanics should make them equivalent and mutually compatible [54]. However, quantum mechanics “does not seem to grant” this, since the former axiom tells us that the post-measurement quantum state of the system will be an eigenstate of the operator corresponding to the measured observable”, whereas the latter leads to an entangled quantum state for the composite system-plus-apparatus. Then, “the system has been sucked into a vortex of entanglement and no longer has its own quantum state. On top of that, the entangled state fails to indicate any particular measurement outcome” (p. 142 [54]).

We add that these Postulates form the basis of the usual quantum mechanics viewpoint on the measuring process (experiment) which Ludwig [50] calls “Registration Procedures and Preparation Procedures” and considers as ‘too one-sided’. This onesidedness Ludwig relates “to the philosophical meaning and interpretation of quantum mechanics, where the measurement process is, of course, a central issue in the problem of meaning” (p. 303. [50]). Let explain the latter. Above we note that the problem of measurement is the problem of measuring one or another, or more unknown properties of a given object. Equivalently, the problem of measurement is to determine whether or not a given object has a given property. This means that a given object under consideration have these properties, at least at the time measurement. These properties can be obviously changed shortly after the measurement due to perturbation of the object by the measurement apparatus. The ideal measurement is that, by definition, this perturbation does not occur.

3.4. Model of Disturbing Measurement

The all discussed in 3.3 depends on the angle from which we look at these statements. Let us look at them from the following another angle and start thinking.

Let a system $S = S_{\text{apparatus}} \cup S_{\text{quantum}}$ be given. $S_{\text{apparatus}}(X)$ is the apparatus subsystem that includes the pointer, and X is subsystem’s generalized coordinate. $S_{\text{quantum}}(x)$ is a quantum subsystem under a measurement performed by the former one, and x is the corresponding generalized coordinate. Let $\Pi(X; x)$ be an arbitrary self-adjoint interaction operator corresponding, according to **Postulate 2** to the observable π . Hence, we may consider Π as the measuring operator. Let $\Psi_i(x)$ be the initial (normalized to unity) state wave function of S_{quantum} belonging to the Hilbert space H . The outcome of a given measurement is $\Psi_m \equiv \Psi_{m(\text{measured})}$, as assumed is also normalized. In the other words, Π maps Ψ_i onto Ψ_m , i. e.,

$$\Pi \Psi_i = \Psi_m^\pi, \Psi_i, \Psi_m \in H. \quad (3)$$

(3) is some type of the generalized eigenvalue problem for the operator Π [81-84]. It is assumed that Ψ_i and Ψ_m both belong to the same Hilbert space H which is partitioned as

$$H = H_i \oplus H_i^\perp \quad (4)$$

where H_i is one-dimensional Hilbert sub-space spanned on Ψ_i over the field \mathbb{C} of complex numbers: $H_i = \mathbb{C}\{\Psi_i\}$, and H_i^\perp is the corresponding orthogonal complement. Therefore, one obtains the decomposition of Ψ_m as follows:

$$\Psi_m^\pi = \lambda \Psi_i + u_m^\pi, \quad (5)$$

where $u_m^\pi \in H_i^\perp$ is defined as an error (bug-)state, and $\langle u_m^\pi | \Psi_i \rangle = 0$. It can be proven by contradiction that if $u_m^\pi = 0$, Ψ_i is the eigenfunction of Π , that is impossible due to the latter arbitrariness²⁷. Hence, $u_m^\pi \neq 0$. ■ (= Q.E.D.). Then, the matrix element of the measuring operator Π in the state Ψ_i , or the expectation value of Π in the state Ψ_i , is equal to²⁸

$$\langle \Psi_i | \Pi | \Psi_i \rangle = \lambda. \quad (6)$$

Under the repeated measurement, one obtains

$$\begin{aligned} \Pi^2 \Psi_i &= \Pi (\lambda \Psi_i + u_m^\pi) = \lambda (\lambda \Psi_i + u_m^\pi) + \Pi u_m^\pi (7') \\ &= \lambda^2 \Psi_i + \lambda u_m^\pi + (\mu u_m^\pi + u_m'), \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where the last expression on the r.h.s. of (7') is represented by that in the last r.h.s. brackets in (7), by analogy with (3) and (5)²⁹. From the latter equations it follows that $u_m^\pi \in H_i^\perp$ and $u_m' \in (H_i^\perp)^\perp$. Due to the latter belonging, one can represent

$$u_m' = \gamma_m^\pi \Psi_i + \Psi_i', \quad (8)$$

²⁷ The case that is referred to **Postulate 3** is excluded from consideration.

²⁸ Margenau (p.469 [35]) treats this as ‘another version’ of the Born rule (see also [85]). Let us recall that the Born rule, or postulate [86-88,35] “introduces a probability concept into

the otherwise deterministic theory and relates it mathematically to the Hilbert space formalism” (p. 197 [86]), under the assumption that the interaction operator Π has a spectrum and the corresponding eigenstates.

²⁹ Actually, Eq. (7) contrasts to the repeatability hypothesis of von Neumann (p. 335 [66]) (see e.g. also [55]).

where the latter is orthogonal to Ψ_i . By analogy with the above proof by contradiction, one can prove that if u_m^π in Eq. (7) is equal to 0, then u_m^π in (7) becomes the eigenfunction of Π . The latter conflicts with Eq. (5) (see also footnote²¹). ■ Hence, γ_m^π in Eq.(8) is not equal to 0.

Therefore,

$$\langle \Psi_i | \Pi^2 | \Psi_i \rangle - (\langle \Psi_i | \Pi | \Psi_i \rangle)^2 = \gamma_m^\pi \equiv \gamma_i^\pi, \quad (9)$$

(9) is the expression of variance [89]. Since $\gamma_m^\pi \neq 0$, this is the case, on the one hand. Let denote this variance as $\Delta\pi(\Psi_i) \neq 0$. On the other, due to that in the probability theory and statistics, the variance is the expected value of the squared deviation from the mean of a random variable, $X_m^\pi = \Pi\Psi_i$ or, equivalently, u_m^π , or a bug state u_m^π is treated as a random variable [89-91]³⁰. Therefore, there exists the uncertainty of measuring of the observable π in the state Ψ_i , due to that the latter behaves under the measurement of the observable π as the modest measurement (5). We formulate this as the following statement:

Proposal 1: If a given state Ψ_i obeys the equations (3) and (5) under the measurement of the observable π that corresponds to the measuring operator Π and if it is not the latter's eigenfunction, then this measurement admits the non-zero uncertainty $\Delta\pi(\Psi_i) = \gamma_i^\pi \neq 0$ in terms of the appropriate variance (9).

Extending Proposal 1 on the momentum, \mathbf{p} , and position, \mathbf{r} , observables, one obtains:

Proposal 2: If a given state Ψ_i obeys the equations (3) and (5) under the measurement of the observable \mathbf{p} that corresponds to the measuring operator \mathbf{P} and if it is not the latter's eigenfunction, then this measurement admits the non-zero uncertainty $\Delta\mathbf{p}(\Psi_i) = \gamma_i^{\mathbf{p}} \neq 0$ in terms of the appropriate variance (9).

and

Proposal 3: If a given state Ψ_i obeys the equations (3) and (5) under the measurement of the observable \mathbf{r} that corresponds to the measuring operator \mathbf{R} and if it is not the latter's eigenfunction, then this measurement admits the non-zero uncertainty $\Delta\mathbf{r}(\Psi_i) = \gamma_i^{\mathbf{r}} \neq 0$ in terms of the appropriate variance (9).

In some sense, **Proposals 2** and **3** remind the Heisenberg's uncertainty principle if these **Proposals** are

valid together. However, they can work separately, either the second or the third, if their corresponding conditions take places. This implies the uncertainty in the measurement either in the momentum or (not and) in position.

4. Afterwords

Whether or not you can observe a thing depends upon the theory you use. It is the theory which decides what can be observed.

*Albert Einstein*³¹

Actually, there are three Afterwords. The first one.

Mermin [58] defined three types of quantum physicists. I don't think I belong to any of them. Although, I am closer to the first type: "(1) those who think quantum mechanics is defaced by a so-called measurement problem", but not quite, I would say, with some bias towards Weinberg, who believed that 'quantum mechanics might need an overhaul' [95].

An example of this is the present work, aimed at a new, *modest interpretation* of the quantum measurement experiment. This is the second Afterword. Within the proposed approach of a measuring experiment, randomness (probability) enters in quantum mechanics throughout a measuring experiment. This fact is rather known (see e.g., [92,93,57]). However, it is distinguished from the traditional viewpoint based on the Projection **Postulate 3**.

The existence of randomness in the experimental measurement event stems from non-zero variance. The measurement experiment is so complex that we refer everything related to the bug-state, Eq.(5), as the random. Although it is just an event with a presumably low, precisely calculated, probability of existence. For this, it is necessary to determine the probability distribution function [89]. Note that randomness is usually interpreted as a poorly calculated probability, where there is not enough data. In this connection - and this is already the third Prologue - I view a quantum object not as phenomenon, but as, according to Kant [23], '*noumenon*', or '*thing-in-itself*' ("Ding an sich" in German, or in English: "thing per se"), which reveal its properties during its observational measuring experiment. Everyone knows Einstein's famous saying "...[t]he theory produces a good deal but hardly brings us closer to the secret of the Old One. I am at all events convinced that *He* does not play dice"³². In view of the present

³⁰ According to the Stanford Encyclopedia of Philosophy (<https://plato.stanford.edu/entries/chance-randomness/>), 'Randomness ... exists when some outcomes occur haphazardly, unpredictably, or by chance (This is reminiscent of the standard phrase: "All coincidences of names, surnames and events are accidental." [or random – ESK]). These latter three notions are all distinct, but all have some kind of close connection to probability. Notoriously, there are many kinds of probability: subjective probabilities ('degrees of belief'), evidential probabilities, and objective chances, to name a few ([94] - ESK), and we might enquire into the connections between randomness and any of these species of probability. In this entry, we focus on the potential connections between randomness and chance, or physical probability... As mentioned in the introduction, some philosophers deliberately use 'random' to mean 'chancy'. A random process, in their view, is

one governed by chance in the sense of the previous section... Chance from a physical point of view implies an event that may or may not happen.'

³¹ Featured in: Albert Einstein Quotes.

³² By these words in his letter to Max Born (December 1926), Einstein expressed his reaction to Born's probabilistic interpretation of quantum mechanics. Once Einstein said this phrase to Bohr to indicate his refusal to accept quantum probabilities. Bohr then argued: "Einstein, stop telling God what to do." Some decades later, Hawking said: "Not only does God play dice, but he sometimes throws them where they cannot be seen." (From The Colour of Time with Marina Amaral, <https://marinaamaral.substack.com/p/einstein-stop-telling-god-what-to>).

modest interpretation of the measurement experiment in quantum mechanics, we may conclude that is exactly the man who creates the experimental apparatus that manifest a random (probabilistic) appearance of a quantum *noumenon*.³³

Acknowledgements

I am pleased to dedicate this article to the 100th anniversary of quantum mechanics [96], in the ‘blossoming’³⁴ development of which Italian physicists played a major role: it suffices to recall the names of E. Fermi, E. Majorana, I. Accardi, E. Agazzi, G. C. Ghirardi, F. Barone, V. Aquilanti, U. Fano, A. Bassi, and many many others [97-100]. I thank Ugo Fano and Enzo Aquilanti for their talks on these events. I take this opportunity to thank Enrico Clementi and Gina Corongiu for their long-term support.

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³³ (Private remark) I have the impression that the *noumenon* of the "thing-in-itself" consists precisely in the concealment

of the measurable property, which entails its indefiniteness, uncertainty.

³⁴ Borrowed from the title of Ref. [98].

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³⁵ It is available on-line at http://www.physik.uni-augsburg.de/annalen/history/historic-papers/1951_443_322-328.pdf. Translation and discussion by K.A. Kirkpatrick,

New Mexico Highlands University, Las Vegas, New Mexico 87701, USA. See also Discussion at the end of [49].

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100. ³⁶ B. Henderson, The Rebel Physicist on the Hunt for a Better Story Than Quantum Mechanics. *The New York Times Magazine*, Feature, June 25, 2020.

³⁶ Excerpt: "The thing that amazes me is that quantum mechanics is only 100 years old," the physicist Angelo Bassi said. We were in conversation across a picnic table on a drab Soviet-era campus in Zagreb, an early-autumn breeze swishing through the yellowing leaves of some nearby trees. "It's a

baby, it's nothing — 100 years in the history of science. How can you just stop there? It doesn't make sense any way you look at it." We sat in the shadow of a rust-stained beige building where Bassi was about to speak at a workshop for physicists who specialize in the century-old subject."